

**MODERN FINANCIAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT: TOOLS FOR
SUSTAINABILITY, INVESTMENT, AND GLOBAL INTEGRATION**

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FINANCIAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

INTRODUCTION

The extent of financial illiteracy among people today, despite the technological revolution, is alarming, distressing touching, and depressing. You'll see that poverty rates are rising daily, despite the fact that there are many billionaires in the globe. Hunger, extreme and abject poverty, and the poverty line are signs that even the richest people on earth amass wealth and money for themselves, and the gap between the rich and the poor is so wide that most of Europe and some nations, such as the UAE, Canada, and the United States, have developed strategies for alleviation to assist their citizens in meeting some of their needs, such as housing, luxurious, benefits of childbearing, health, etc. Why, therefore, is poverty present there? Because we all deal with money on a daily basis, financial management should be taught at all levels of the educational system, from primary to high school and university. According to a study, the majority of people who win the financial lottery in the West fail to invest their winnings wisely and return to poverty after a period of time.

For personal use, having the ability to manage money is crucial because it is a necessity. Your ability to engage in financial savings, creation, directive, organization, control, and involvement in a secured investment that will generate a solid return or profit will be improved more as a result of this program. Additionally, it will assist you in minimizing or avoiding financial risk in daily financial activities and market transactions. Due to this, managing financial resources is crucial for making decisions because it helps you understand your level of preference and how to make the most of your income in order to eradicate poverty.

Therefore, regular saving and depositing is necessary for each individual depending on the situation in order to reap benefits like interest for bonds, long and short durations. For each person to be free from the shackles of financial uncertainty, it must become a habit. It is important to make a secured investment, such as one in real estate, government bonds, lending firms, banking profits, or one of these.

In my opinion, this component of finance, I'm talking about financial management is just as important as financial accounting, which focuses on the future by dealing with

past transactions, if not more so. Every time, we must choose the proper course of action.

Difference between Financial Accounting and Financial Management

Financial management and financial accounting are two distinct financial responsibilities, with financial accounting requiring the reporting of previous financial transactions. Financial management, in contrast, necessitates planning for upcoming transactions.

A specialized area of economics called finance deals with the creation and administration of money, credit, banking, and investment. The acquisition and management of cash and assets are the focus of the study and practice of finance. Financial experts deal with how money is invested and spent.

The chief financial officer (CFO), an executive in a senior position, is a financial manager who is in charge of all accounting and financial operations. They might create financial plans, keep tabs on transactions, or offer advice on ways to make the company's finances better.

The three branches of financial management are;

- Capital budgeting: The purpose of capital budgeting is to determine the financial requirements for the company's short- and long-term goals.
- Capital structure: The company's capital structure defines how to finance its operations and/or expansion.
- Working capital management: Management of working capital: This relates to the operating finances that keep the business afloat.

The term "finance" refers to issues involving the management, production, research, and investment of money. This entails the use of credit and debt, securities and investments to finance ongoing projects while forecasting and predicting the company's financial future using future income flow.

In a similar vein, the term "finance" is essentially a catch-all for several facets of money. It can be characterized roughly as the study of the subject of creation management, as well as the study of money, currency, and capital assets.

What is Financial Management?

Planning, arranging, directing, and controlling a company's financial resources to meet its objectives constitutes financial management.

In order to maximize profits and minimize risk, it is the proper use of an organization's financial resources, including selecting investments and implementing cash management strategy(ies).

What is the process of financial management?

- Setting financial goals, predicting future cash flow, and figuring out how to successfully and precisely reach them are all part of financial planning.
- Budgeting entails developing a financial strategy and allocating resources to meet the overall financial and economic objectives with the help of several departments or sectors.
- Investment choices: despite the difficulties, this entails selecting which assets, such as stocks, bonds, real estate, etc., to invest in order to maximize profits while limiting risk.
- Management of the capital structure entails choosing the best proportion of debt and equity to use to finance the expansion and ongoing operations of the company. Despite the dangers and market trends, if necessary.
- Making decisions on how to invest excess cash and managing liquidity are both essential components of good cash management. It might refer to diversity, distributing the extra money among profitable investments.
- Financial reporting: A component of financial management is the creation of financial statements and reports to stakeholders on the financial performance of the firm. Transparency, accountability, etc. are brought about through this.
- Risk management entails determining and controlling the organization's financial risks, such as credit risk, interest rate risk, etc.
- To meet the financial objectives of the firm and optimize shareholder value (return, profit, dividend, etc.), financial management combines and coordinates various tasks.

A source of finance is a source of funding made available to a firm to meet its operating needs. This includes working capital for the short term, fixed assets, and other long-term investments.

- Finance,
- Banking
- Leverage
- Credit
- Capital market
- Money
- Investment

FOUR TYPES OF FINANCE

- ✓ Personal finance
- ✓ Corporate finance
- ✓ Public finance(Government)
- ✓ Nonprofits/ Charity finance

Financial services are used by both consumers and corporations to obtain financial goods and accomplish financial objectives. The primary engine of a country's economy is the financial services industry. Banking is a particular subset of finance, and banking is centered on managing depositories, loans, and other financial products and services offered by banks. This is one of the main distinctions between banking and finance. A wider variety of activities connected to money management and investing fall under the umbrella of finance.

Importance of Financial management.

- To achieve your business financial goal.
- To help in decision making.
- To maintain financial stability.
- To maximize the shareholders returns
- To improve transparency and accountability.
- To ensure compliance.
- It also save guides individual , organization, government from risks(wastage)
- It helps in the diversity of surplus funds for market investments, which leads to more employment.

Economic: the condition of a nation or region with regard to the creation and consumption of commodities and services as well as the availability of money. Any business or nation that wants to succeed with its citizens economically must manage its resources carefully.

FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

The task of financial management is to allocate the available financial resources so as to maximize business success and return on investment (ROI). All corporate transactions are planned, organized, and controlled by financial management professionals. With a team of knowledgeable financial management professionals, the national economy can be managed successfully.

These are the five categories of financial management:

- Corporate financial management is concerned with choosing the best combination of debt and equity for an organization's financing and investments in order to maximize returns on investment.
- Personal financial management: This focuses on managing an individual's financial resources, including setting a budget, saving money, making investments, and safeguarding assets through estate planning and insurance.

- Public financial management: This focuses on government organizations and includes planning budgets, collecting taxes, and managing spending.
- International financial management : The financing and investment of international activities, as well as the management of currency risks and foreign investment decisions, are dealt with in this area of financial management.
- Financial management of non-profit organizations, such as foundations, charities, religious institutions, the World Health Organization, the United Nations, and its departments, is included in this category of financial management. It also includes fund-raising and grant management.

THE 10 FUNCTIONS OF FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

- Estimation of the capital required
- Determination of the capital structure
- Choice of the source of funds
- Procurement of financial resources
- Utilization of funds
- Disposal of surplus funds or profits
- Management of cash
- Financial control
- Reports of every transaction, statements to the stakeholders or the public if the need be
- Forecast and predict accurately based on past transaction and market trends.

The financial management is generally concerned with procurement, allocation and control of financial resources of a concern. Objectives can be to ensure regular and adequate supply of funds to the concern

The basic 3 functions a financial manager are as follows

- Investment decisions

- Financial decisions
- Dividend decisions

THE FIVE PRINCIPLES

- Consistency
- Timeliness
- Justification
- Documentation
- Certification or (check and balance)

Investment or secured investment?

Due to the abundance of available investments, many investors are rushing to make investments because they think the return or value profit would be worthwhile. For this reason, certain professionals focus their job and activities on investments, both of the actual and immaterial variety. equities, securities, shares, bonds, long-term and short-term loans, bank deposits, houses for resale or rental, mortgages for subsequent re-mortgages, particularly in the west, education, and rentals like halls, uber, among others. Beyond this, it also includes politics, government, large corporations, and multinational businesses.

As beneficial as these investments are, there are a lot of risks associated with them. On the other hand, other investments carry less risk. As a result, it is your responsibility as an individual to decide what you want to invest in based on your available funds or financing. Of course, most billionaires contact professionals for advice on investments, so you must be prepared to pay them.

In the meantime, risky investments such as stocks, shares, securities, etc., require careful monitoring and precise forecasts.

According to the Pareto principle of ratio, 80:20, if well-informed decisions are taken into consideration before making the investment, the effective and proper articulation of the 20 investment can give 80% return.

For an individual, an institution, or the government to avoid losing money while minimizing risk or, better yet, opting for a secured investment with no risk, it is required to engage financial management.

In instance, some people believe that the more labor you put in, the greater the profit. However, I believe that a secured investment can help you control risk.

IN INVESTMENT WE HAVE THREE TYPES

- Upward investment
 - Downward investment
 - Horizontal investment
-
- Upward investment is when you put money into a larger organization, something that is greater than you, in order to share in the dividends. Such leverage is referred to as an upward investment, such as purchasing Coca-Cola shares, MTN, government bonds, etc.

An individual or an investment that you know will pay off soon, such as a new venture firm, biotechnology company, established new school or university, furniture company, small business or industry, is considered a downward investment.

- Horizontal investment It is about partnerships, in which two banks work together to create a bank, such when Stanbic IBTC in South Africa formed an alliance with IBTC, an insurance firm. You can see that both of them were established organizations before they engaged in financial activity, and that they have since become larger and more diverse. Thus, it becomes Stanbic IBTC bank; their directors made this horizontal investment.

ASSETS AND LIABILITIES

Understanding the distinction between an asset and a liability is crucial. Investments produce returns, profits, and financial growth whereas liabilities lose value over time as a result of use and inflation.

In order to create funds and diversify their surplus, financial resource managers must be critical in their thinking and evaluation before making investment decisions. Your selection will have an impact on you in terms of all financial matters. You will be held accountable, accused, and condemned for anything that goes wrong. You are therefore encouraged to understand every investment you advise your clients or business to make and to be well-informed about it.

In the same way, while communicating about financial management, you should talk to your director, team leader, and managing director in addition to the shareholder. The downward financial communicator deals with you and conveys the work task to your junior employees in your department or other sector within the same organization, whereas the horizontal financial communicators are those conversations you have with your coworkers in your workplace and other organizations.

MANAGING FINANCE

The fund manager or financial manager is the person who prepares, organizes, coordinates, and manages the distribution of these finances, and the competence that is required is financial management. If an organization genuinely wants to continue operating, its financial load will be heavy. The majority of businesses that fail or enter a state of liquidity do so due to improper or inconsistent management of their financial operations.

As long as the flow of capital is yielding and managed, the company's existence is secure. However, once there are gaps in the transaction activities, it won't be long before they become evident and some managers or directors will embezzle the company's funds. Even for the CEO, this is a huge problem.

FINANCIAL ASSETS

Do you find this surprising? I am confident that you are well aware of your assets, including buildings, land, investments, and tangible and intangible assets. Assets are valuable and come with a price tag; they are what you can utilize as leverage and sell for either appreciation or depreciation.

Financial assets, on the other hand, are financial records that may be exchanged for cash or their equivalent and are used as a down payment, guarantee, or surety to protect loans and some types of enterprises. These financial records are valuable assets that are widely accepted and recognized.

Bonds, certificates of deposit, shares, loan securities, mortgage documents, account statements, insurance certificates, contract documents, partnership agreements, etc. are a few examples of these financial assets.

These financial documents, which I will refer to as financial assets, can be bought, traded, and used as security. Everything depends on how much money is in the document and what someone wants to use it for.

The British government, in particular their migration department, requires that school fees and a specific amount of money be deposited in your account statement for a period of 28 days in order to obtain a student visa. As a result, the 28-day statement of accounts is a real financial asset that, when submitted along with other requirements, secures a student visa for the program.

In financial management, we look beyond the immediate future. Once you have a clear understanding of the financial architecture of past transactions, you can foresee and predict the reality and stability of the future for an individual, a corporate entity, or the government as a whole.

This assists in choosing the appropriate productive policies for economic growth, human wellbeing, and sustainability. Due to the fact that managing financial assets will improve leverage when necessary, growth and development will be improved.

Consequently, a financial asset is a liquid item whose value is based on a legal claim to ownership or a contractual right, such as cash, stocks, bonds, mutual funds, or bank deposits.

Bank loans, direct investments, and government private ownership of debt and equity securities and other instruments are examples of financial assets.

The financial investment, however, is counted in both countries' foreign investment positions when the holder lives in a different nation than the one that issued it.

The two countries' trade agreement on investment will serve as a guarantor for a guarantee of financial returns or value. The foreign investment will be safeguarded as a result.

FINANCIAL CHALLENGES

Every aspect of our world, including households, workplaces, large organizations, and the governments of many countries throughout the world, engages in conversation about this issue on a daily basis. In fact, the rich want more, the rate of inflation is increasing daily, and societal trends in technology, economy, and culture have threatened the finances of individuals, corporate entities, businesses, families, and the government, among others. In the face of these financial challenges, it is essential to keep the government functioning and stabilized, as well as the business in full operation to prevent it from shutting down. The difficulties are overwhelming and vary from one location to another.

Additionally, this has contributed to the widespread migration of labor from one nation to another. The investors are looking for better locations that would improve their returns and excess fund in order to confront these financial issues. It also led to changes in jobs in pursuit of a better life and decent income.

How can one, as a financial manager, deal with these financial difficulties for themselves, for corporate entities, for the government, and for everyone else?

In order to overcome financial obstacles, it is necessary to have the insights and strategies.

FINANCIAL STRATEGY

Every competent financial manager should be able to think strategically, thus they should be informed on the state of the economy, changes in governmental policies, global commerce, the operations of the central bank and their stances, among other things. To change if necessary to a more advantageous investment and provide the proper guidance through a well-defined choice that will be fruitful and efficient for surplus cash.

Loans with low interest rates and long terms, for instance, can be particularly beneficial to a business owner, shareholders, and the government when there are financial difficulties.

This method of money raising can aid in the gathering of finances for both new and established businesses. For individuals that adhere to the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations, there are numerous incentives available.

A portion of the company's shares may be made available to the general public in order to raise money for investments in diversity that will increase profitability. This might take place following stakeholder consultation and stock exchange regulation compliance.

Put your attention on the top return products and services.

The manager of financial resources can persuade the company to concentrate all of its resources on the product that is most profitable out of all of its offerings. This will increase the amount of surplus money.

DEALING WITH EXPENDITURE

Expenditure can be reduced as a method of solving financial obstacles.

A competent specialist in financial resources management will be able to connect to the organization or government to view events from a distance via an economic lens and place himself and the business in a favorable position.

When you see that rain is coming, you can plan ahead by collecting more buckets, drains, reserves, etc. to collect as much water as you can so that you can take full advantage of the circumstance. There will be an abundance.

On the other hand, if you notice that it is about to rain and you ignore it, you will fill the five buckets with water. You can borrow money to buy drums, reservoirs, etc. when you only have five buckets because you can forecast by observing the market system, governmental laws, etc. Financial management deals with the present and future through the past transactions.

WHAT IS STRATEGY?

A course of action intended to accomplish a long-term or overall goal, such as a road map for a company and how she intends to get there. To attain the planned and intended aim or goals, there must be systematic ways, mannerisms, and structures that are safeguarded for operational activities that will be effective and efficient for higher performance. The strategies and methodical, detailed course of action must be followed in order to achieve the organizational goal.

FINANCIAL PRODUCT POOL

You have to understand the range of financial products. These are a few different sources of income. To find the one that would be advantageous for investment at the correct time, you must conduct a brainstorming session among the product pools. What are the seasonal changes in demand, supply, and price, and may an organization use some of the funds allocated by the government for a deposit in a bank or a loan company? Which industries are now profitable? What is the company's projected financial goal for the year? Knowing the benchmarks, measures of value, and other

factors will enable you to obtain insight into the financial product pool and make an informed decision before making a secured investment.

INTERNATIONAL FINANCE

The study of monetary interactions between two or more countries is known as international finance. The trade agreement will increase the economic value or equity, whether it be within the same continent or another continent.

International finance therefore focuses on topics like foreign direct investment and currency exchange rates.

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERNATIONAL FINANCE

By assisting in the determination of exchange rates, which are based on the relative values of currencies, as well as by adhering to the (IFRS) International Financial Reporting Standard system, which aids in the reporting of financial issues globally, international finance contributes to the maintenance of economic relations between various nations. Regional currencies like the Euro and foreign direct investment are two examples of international finance. via means of a legal transaction, such as an investment by a firm in another nation.

Three key objectives of the IMF are as follows:

1. To support international monetary corporations
2. to promote increased trade and economic development.
3. to oppose measures that might impair economic development.

Domestic businesses entail economic transactions that take place within a nation's borders, whereas international businesses involve economic transactions that take place outside.

The three principal institutions of international finance are.

the World Bank

The International Finance Corporation

the International Monetary Fund

The largest IFI nowadays is the European Investment Bank, which provided Global Project with a loan of €61 billion in 2011.

When studying international trade finance, you should become familiar with these four foundations. Four pillars serve as a potentially effective way to explain the value proposition related to the fundamentals of international trade finance.

- Payments
- Risks
- mitigation
- Financing and information.

Because sovereign nations have the right and authority to issue their own currencies, create their own economic policies, and impose taxes, these risks play a large role in the world of international finance.

regulates and taxes people's movements. beyond their frontiers. The financial resources manager must have access to current and pertinent information for a variety of reasons, among them. Loss, investment, and protection for the company's gain.

THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL FINANCE MANAGER

An international finance manager should assess the risks associated with project gains that are uncertain as a result of various other factors, including exchange control, remittance restrictions, political risk, different tax systems, sources of funds, exchange rate fluctuations, and inflation ratios. These factors are likely to have a negative impact on a company's value.

We also have (9) major types of financial institutions, such as.

- Insurance companies
- Credit unions
- Mortgage companies
- Investment banks
- brokerage firms
- Central banks
- Internet banks
- Savings and loan companies.
- Commercial Banks

Studying international financial management will equip you with transferable abilities that will enable you to work in a variety of natural and economic hubs all over the world. You'll gain a wide perspective and comprehension of the shifting nature and role of finance in the context of a global marketplace.

For example. In Nigeria. We have different type of financial institutions that are supervised by the Central Bank of Nigeria CBN. They are;

Bureaux-de-change (BDCs)

Commercial Banks

Development financial institutions(DFIs)

Discount houses

finance companies.

Holding Companies (HCs)

Merchants Banks

Microfinance Banks (MFBs).

The method used for international business for their international operations are

- Import /Exports
- Licensing
- Franchising
- Management Contract
- Joint ventures
- Foreign Direct Investment

Either by acquisition or greenfield start-up

International Business Environment matters , the factors to be considered are
geographical conditions
cultural and societal factors
Political and legal factors
economic condition.

The seven Cs to take into consideration, which also involves international customers, cost, competitors ,culture, channels, currency and comparability. The seven C's, of international pricing that must be considered.

DIGITAL FINANCE

The term "digital finance" is used to describe how new technologies have affected the financial services sector. The traditional method of providing banking and financial services has been revolutionized by a wide range of products, apps, processes, and business models.

Financial technology innovation is not a new phenomenon, but investments in new technologies have significantly expanded in recent years, and innovation is occurring at an exponential rate. We now communicate with our bank via mobile technology, and we use a number of modern technologies that weren't available a few years ago to send payments, transfer money, and make investments.

Artificial intelligence, social networks, machine learning, mobile apps, distributed ledger technology, cloud computing, and big data analytics have sparked the development of new services and business models by both incumbent financial institutions and up-and-coming competitors.

By enabling more access to financial services, expanding the range of options, and improving operational efficiency, all these technologies can be advantageous to businesses as well as consumers. In sectors like internet banking, online payments,

and transfer services, they can also help break down national boundaries and promote competition.

- peer to peer lending - services and advice for individual investments.

FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY

Financial sustainability is the ability of a business to generate income or receive a return on investment that pays for all costs and generates a profit. It determines whether or not spending resources in a project will yield a suitable return for investors.

Four pillars of Financial Sustainability by future learn are;

Human

Social

Economics

Environmental

According to LinkedIn, viability is what separates financial sustainability from that. Sustainability is the ability of something to continue existing while being beneficial to neither the economy nor the environment nor society. Seegera strikes a balance between preservation, neighborhood, culture, and business, and she places the environment at the center of the development. Kruger Cowne Limited

In other words, whatever you do must take into account the environment, which indicates that the environment cannot be harmed in the pursuit of financial gain. The concept of financial sustainability exists because both living and non-living things are present in your surroundings, including people, animals, plants, land, climate, and water. Don't conduct business in a way that seriously harms the environment.

CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS

- Cross border transaction.
- Two or more countries are involved in the business
- Global as well as domestic competition.
- Use of foreign currencies based on a free market economy
- Import/ export of international products
- Free flow of factors of production.

Therefore, international finance is a section of financial economics that deals with the macroeconomic relation between two countries and their monetary value.

The features of international finance

The features of International Finance are transmitting capital, transacting with allotments, proper money utilization, procurement, maximizing investors, wealth, cross border payments, international banking, trade finance.

and efficient economic management.

The risks that associated with international finance are, currency, political and market rates. Moreover. These challenges can lead to fluctuation in exchange rates, increased volatility in financial markets, and potential losses due to unexpected events.

INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL BUSINESS

Every transaction you will employ must be in the framework of international financial business, therefore there is no way that you can engage in international finance without dealing with the operations of international company. Additionally, this will transcend national boundaries, cultural differences, monetary systems, rate of exchanges, various commercial contracts, etc.

The need to find a favorable and acceptable method of payments that are supported legally by the involved companies and their home countries is very important and a

concern for every organization and financial resource management manager because of the size of the financial transactions in the international financial businesses.

To prevent wastage of provided goods and services, it is necessary to minimize the risks associated with doing business internationally. For the goal of mitigation, the dos and don'ts of the involved countries must be clearly stated.

However, due of the exchange conversion rate, doing business internationally is incredibly successful and profitable. However, it must be complied with before either products or services are delivered.

THE SIX CRITERIA, SUSTAINABILITY

This includes social equity, economic viability, and environmental protection. Similarly, there are six factors involved in this concept, which are

- Climate change
- Environment
- Innovation
- Technology
- People
- Ethics
- Human rights

The principles of sustainable construction as an example of sustainability includes, Sustainable design.

- Durability.
- Energy efficiency,
- waste reduction,
- Indoor air quality,
- water conservation,
- Sustainable materials.

The above were published as Build bass

Financial sustainability is crucial since it will protect us from being directly or indirectly detrimental to the organization's financial objectives. To ensure that an organization's actions are not unlawful, punishable by fines, disruptive to the peace, etc., additional criteria must be taken into account and regulated. Because they may cause the government to seal the corporation.

FUND MANAGEMENT

The management of a financial institution's cash flow is referred to as fund management. The fund manager makes sure that the demand for loans and the deposit maturity schedule are in sync. Financial management's primary objectives are to make sure a business is both effective and profitable. To do this, the manager considers both the liability and the assets that affect the bank's capacity to issue credit. Additionally, it aims to maximize profit, stakeholders' returns, compliance with regulations, and total firm value while monitoring liquidity and cash flow.

The functions of fund management include

A fund manager is in charge of carrying out the investment strategy for the fund and overseeing its trading activity. They manage analysts, undertake data-driven research, oversee mutual funds or pensions, and make crucial financial decisions. The necessity of managing ongoing finances, which I will refer to as operational and surplus funds, in order to prevent the director from wasting money on luxuries, departmental theft of funds, etc. Therefore, when there is effective management, the company will be sustained and protected from business issues, and it will undoubtedly grow.

FINANCIAL INVESTMENT AND TOOLS

Instead of just one asset, it might be a collection of capital used for investment. These are all assets that may be traded by investors, whether they are physical objects like real estate or debt contracts.

Financial inclusion refers to the availability to both individuals and businesses of useful and reasonably priced financial goods and services that suit their needs. Examples include transaction, payment, savings credit, and insurance services that are provided in an ethical and sustainable manner. According to the World Bank Overview definition, financial inclusion is a term used to describe the process of removing obstacles that prevent people from accessing the financial sector and its products in order to better their lives. According to Investopedia Finance, it is also known as inclusive finance.

The goal of Financial Tools is to help your business manage its assets, income, and expenses in order to maximize profitability. According to usage and requirements, some of the most popular financial tools are common size statements (vertical analysis), comparison financial statements, ratio analysis (quantitative analysis), cash flow analysis, and trend analysis by Wall Street Mojo.

Exchange-traded funds (ETFs), mutual funds, and real estate investment trusts (REITs) are all examples of financial investments. Bonds, derivative agreements (such futures, options, and swaps), cheques, certificates of deposit (CDs), and loans.

These investments are divided into two types

- Cash instruments and
- Derivative instruments.
- Some categories of these financial instruments are ;
- Money market investments,
- debt securities instruments,
- equity securities instruments,
- derivative instruments,
- foreign exchange instruments.
- shares, stock, bonds, features and options, contract, etc.

Financial assets are split into the following financial instruments

- Monetary gold and SDR
- Currency and deposits
- Debt securities
- Loans

- Equity and investment fund shares or units
- Insurance, pension and standardized guarantee
- Financial derivatives and employee stock option

For example an entity that sells goods on credit issues an invoice (piece of paper) represents a financial instrument and in particular a financial assets-the debtor or receivable.

Design your own financial instrument

1. Identify the proposed amount and the expected leverage effect
2. Choose the proposed financial products
3. Identify and describe the proposed target group of final recipients
4. Describe the expected contribution to the specific objectives

These are some techniques for creating your own financial instrument.

Financial assets include things like money in the form of bank deposits, equities, bonds, and mutual funds.

As a result, the agreement is a statutory agreement rather than a contractual agreement that involves receiving or paying VAT. Since it does not result from a contractual agreement, VAT receivable or payable is not a financial instrument.

You will be able to manage organizational funds, money, and assets effectively and efficiently by making the appropriate selections if you have a proper understanding of financial instruments.

Five types of financial reports and their benefits for business

1. Balance sheet
2. Income statement
3. Cash flow statement
4. Statement of changes in capital
5. Notes to financial statement

The beneficial performance of the financial management manager will be boosted by the requirement for financial reports, reviews, and evaluators through consistent analysis for a better understanding through facts and figures, balance of statements, and openness in all financial activities.

Because of this, the financial report and review will also aid in assessments for judgments to be made on all pertinent issues for the growth, administration, and sustainability of the business objective. For adequate, precise, and suitable forecasting for the organizational investments, it is crucial to carefully examine the financial instruments, resources, and overall cash in operation with the financial statement.

INVESTMENT MANAGEMENT

Investment management, which aims to achieve certain investment goals for the benefit of investors, is the professional management of various securities, including share holdings, bonds, and other assets, such as real estate. Because of this, a financial manager must properly consider all the information before making any decisions on the company's investment.

In conjunction with the financial statement planning prediction, an investment manager, who is also the financial management manager, can help an individual or an organization with administrative tax issues, cash flow management, and the distribution of funds in the future. The manager of financial resources must make investment decisions before making any investments and managing them. Research, asset selection, oversight, and management of a portfolio of assets that are in line with the organization's objectives, risk tolerance, and time period will be required.

However risk management happens when a fund manager or investor assesses and makes an effort to quantify the possibility of losses in an investment, such as a moral hazard, and then decides what course of action (or inactivity) to follow given the fund's investment objectives and risk tolerance.

FUND MANAGEMENT

The management and control of a financial institution's cash flow is what this is. The fund manager makes sure that the deposit maturity dates and the lending demand are in sync.

The management does this by examining the assets and liabilities that affect the bank's ability to extend credit.

FUND TRANSFER

A sequence of transactions that move money from the sender to the recipient is referred to as a fund transfer. It can also be described as the transfer of money from one party to another or to itself using the financial system. Automated Teller Machines (ATM), payroll systems with direct deposit, and business-to-business direct payments are a few examples.

Different methods to transfer fund online

- Immediate payment service (IMPS)
- National electronic fund transfer (NEFT)
- Real-time gross settlement (RTGS)

The customer instructs their bank to transfer the appropriate money to the business bank account, together with the special reference number identifying the transfer's objective. The bank of the customer transfers money to the business bank. The money is deposited into the account of the company or other person, who records the retrieval.

Another word for transfer of funds are

- Remittance
- Transmitted
- Discharge
- Sending
- Nailing
- Transfer

- Release
- Dispatch
- Transmission
- Consignment

Etc

Agencies generally use the automated clearing house (ACH) system for computerized fund transfers. EFT and ACH allow for online payments and electronic fund transfers to banking institutions. Consequently, we'll talk about an EFT. When money is transferred electronically between bank accounts, whether inside a single financial institution or among several, it is done through computer-based systems and takes place without the direct involvement of bank employees.

Type of Electronic Fund Transfer Payments

ACH direct deposit: this is used to pay employee paychecks from employers

ACH direct payments

ACH direct debits

Wire transfer

ATM transaction

Debit cards

Credit cards

Peer-to peer payment

Any electronic payment sent using bank account information

Online application for receiving and payment e.g opay, palm-pay, kuda etc.

A debit card system works similarly to an electronic payments transfer system. The payer must enroll in an electronic funds transfer system and make sure their accounts have the required credit in every transaction.

Electronic Fund Transfer payments are incredibly safe, just as ATM transactions and direct deposits of paychecks. All payment information is sent through a secure communications channel and encrypted using 128-bit SSL.

The type of bank transactions includes

- Cash withdrawals

- Cash deposits
- Checks
- Online payments
- Debit card charges
- Wire transfer
- Loan payment
- Direct investment on standing order
- Insurance direct payment
- Transfer from foreign currency to domestic currency payment.

Fund Transfer Periods

Money is normally transferred swiftly; domestic bank wires typically take no longer than three days to complete. Less than 24 hours may be required for transfers between accounts at the same bank or financial institution.

On the other hand, a wire transfer made possible by a non-bank money transfer provider like internet banking may take place immediately.

In fact, if the network is operating normally, you should see the money in seconds. For this reason, most people choose more efficient and secure methods of transferring money; however, the level of caution that should be exercised depends on how much money is being transferred and to which jurisdiction, region, country, or international organization.

This is because mistakes, fraud, scams, and other errors can still be traced, but it will take longer to resolve, rectify, amend, and confront the offender due to differences in jurisdiction, domain, region, and country, as well as interventions brought on by various laws, policies, cultures, procedures, and other processes that will make the financial rectification of the transferred funds more difficult once it has been sent. As a result, exercising caution and due diligence when transferring money is more important.

FINANCIAL DIVERSITY

In the financial sector, diversity is gradually expanding, but not quickly enough. Although the proportion of Black and Latino CFPs increased by over 13% between 2019 and 2020, black professionals still make up only a little more than 2% of all CFPs. Accounting representation is slightly better, according to Forbes

By creating an ideal portfolio, the variety principle or financial diversity helps to reduce risk. Never place all of your eggs in one basket because if it falls, all of your eggs will shatter. Instead, place your eggs in many baskets so that your risk is reduced. The act of ensuring that procedures and business plans are unbiased, just, and give each person the best potential outcomes is known as guaranteeing equity. Creating a sense of belonging among employees is known as inclusion. Diversity is the presence of distinctions within a particular context.

According to the CFP board's analysis, people who work for a variety of organizations are frequently happier than those who don't. A quicker hiring process and more responsibility at these firms are also correlated with this high degree of employee engagement. Consider this: High turnover has an opportunity cost, according to Forbes.

Inclusion is just as crucial in investment banking recruitment as diversity since a diverse team may provide a wide range of viewpoints and experiences that can help clients negotiate difficult regulatory settings.

In conclusion, a manager of financial resources must diversify funds to reduce investment risk. This diversification, however, must be done gradually.

Because of this, the majority of financial managers are enquiring, intelligent, and detail-oriented before engaging with any certain company or organization. Prior to making an investment selection, it is imperative to conduct careful thought. If a certified financial professional (CFP) wants to be trusted with money and the future of the organization's business, they must be honest, open, trustworthy, responsible, etc. The company will be impacted by a single theft of funds, whether it be cash flow, capital, etc., and the results could harm the organization's reputation.

Because of this, some businesses fail, enter liquidation, and shut down completely. Mismanagement, appropriation without authorization, shifting funds to personal use, etc. To view and manage money, its surplus, and with the access you as a financial manager have, while remaining trustworthy, takes a lot of high discipline and integrity. That is being professional.

I would advise everyone who completes this program to avoid engaging in any financial misbehavior and to act professionally since billionaires are looking for people with strong financial ethics who they can work with and hire.

